

Local Variations in Current Density and Selectivity in CO₂ Electrolyzers

Published as part of ACS Energy Letters *special issue* “The Evolving Landscape of Energy Research: Views from the Editorial Team”.

Pedro Arias Villaroel, Egon Kecszenovity, and Csaba Janáky*

Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenerylett.5c03770>

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: As CO₂ electrolysis emerges as a key technology for industrial decarbonization, scaling from lab to industrial systems introduces challenges beyond increasing the active area or the CO₂ feed rate. Larger reactors often exhibit spatial inhomogeneities in selectivity and current density, issues overlooked in conventional performance studies. To address this, we designed, built, and tested a zero-gap flow cell for CO₂ electrolysis that enables local monitoring of the product selectivity and current density. Gas composition is sampled at multiple points along the flow path, while current density is tracked across the cell. This approach reveals where and under what conditions parasitic hydrogen evolution occurs. In this work we present how operating parameters influence localized product formation and current density profiles in a CO₂-to-CO electrolyzer. Our findings emphasize the importance of moving beyond averaged metrics to achieve efficient, uniform operation across the cell, an essential step for successful scale-up.

CO₂ electrolysis offers a promising route to convert captured CO₂ into chemical feedstocks by using green electricity. As the technology advances, industrially relevant current densities have been demonstrated, together with selective and increasingly durable electrolyzers capable of stable operation. Moreover, coupling CO₂ electrolysis with intermittent renewable energy sources has been shown feasible, paving the way toward cost-competitive and sustainable carbon dioxide conversion.^{1–4}

As this technology continues to emerge, the need arises to replicate electrolyzer performance from the lab scale to industrial-scale systems.^{5,6} This transition, however, is far from a simple matter of scaling up the active area and increasing the CO₂ feed rate. As reactor dimensions increase, gradients in temperature, pressure, and concentration begin to play a dominant role in electrolyzer performance—also resulting in spatial inhomogeneities in current density and selectivity. These issues are negligible at the lab scale, where the cell size is small enough for parameters such as (partial) pressure, velocity, and temperature to remain essentially uniform throughout the electrolyzer.

Moreover, scaling up introduces the difficulty of relying on bulk measurements—such as overall current or outlet gas compositions at the cathode and anode—that represent only averaged values, representative for the entire active area. In reality, local variations in selectivity, current density, and ion transport may occur across the electrode area, in the form of

gradients or hot-spots, yet these are masked in the collective signal recorded at the outlet.^{7,8}

Such spatial phenomena have been thoroughly studied in both fuel cells and water electrolyzers.^{9–13} These devices, however, are substantially different from those of CO₂ electrolyzers. In the H₂ fuel cell case, two gas phase reactants are fed, and a liquid product (water) is removed.¹⁴ In water electrolyzers, a liquid phase reactant is fed, and two gas phase products are removed.¹⁵ In stark contrast, in the most advanced zero-gap CO₂ electrolyzers, both liquid and gas feedstocks are provided; and, in the CO₂-to-CO case discussed below, a gas phase product is formed.¹⁶ Having such fundamental differences means that the conclusions drawn for fuel cells and water electrolyzers are not directly applicable to CO₂ electrolysis. Furthermore, as we move toward industrial implementation and larger cells/stack, effective management and understanding of reaction and transport conditions across the cell become crucial.

Based on the above arguments, methods for analyzing local current density and selectivity (i.e., product distribution) are now more important than ever. Conventional cell architectures

Received: November 14, 2025

Revised: December 18, 2025

Accepted: December 22, 2025

Figure 1. Schematic of the cell concept. (A) Cross-sectional view of the cell (left) and exploded view of the main cell components: (1) cathodic end plate, (2) printed cathodic insulator, (3) printed anodic insulator, (4) anodic end plate, (5) anode current collector made of stainless steel, (6) Ir-coated titanium porous transport electrode, PTE (7) anion exchange membrane, AEM, (8) gas diffusion electrode, GDE, (9) segmented cathode current collector, based on a printed circuit board equipped with (10) 32 individual segments, that measure the current density, and (11) 7 sampling points distributed across the length of the cell. (B) Schematics of the zero-gap cell concept: (I) Segments are built in the (II) PCB body and in contact with the (III) GDE. The (IV) AEM is pressed in between the GDE and (V) PTE, and the (VI) anodic current collector closes the cell on the other side. (C) Simplified electrical operation concept. Individual segments or areas of the cell ($\times 1$, $\times 2$, $\times 3$, etc.) comprise an electrical load that can be simplified as a resistance. As these change with a varying environment, the applied voltage to the whole cell will make the current distribute accordingly.

provide only spatially averaged data, and dimension-dependent effects must therefore be investigated through alternative approaches. While local overpotentials, current density distributions, and selectivity gradients are often studied using Multiphysics and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models, such models rely on assumptions that may not accurately capture real operating behavior.^{17–19}

To address this challenge, we designed, built, and tested a locally resolved CO₂RR electrolyzer cell featuring a segmented cathode current collector capable of mapping current density distribution in real time, combined with seven sampling points in the cathode chamber for online analysis of the gas products (Figure 1A,B). This setup allows simultaneous spatial and temporal monitoring of the current density and selectivity. For the sake of amplifying spatial effects, we did not introduce a gas flow field in the first iteration of the design.

Local current density distribution and local cathode gas concentration are of particular interest in CO₂ electrolysis for several reasons. On the one hand, there exists the side reaction of hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which competes with CO₂ reduction and can become dominant under certain conditions, such as an improper management of electrolyte content in the gas diffusion electrode (GDE).²⁰ This process not only enhances mass transport limitations but also increases the apparent cathodic activation resistance toward CO₂ reduction, as the partial current density toward C-based products decreases, and the reaction pathway shifts towards the HER.¹⁷ On the other hand, unlike in water electrolysis, CO₂ is directly gas-fed into the cell, so its partial pressure, a key driver of its accessibility to active sites, gradually decreases from inlet to outlet due to product formation, carbonate ion migration through the anion exchange membrane (AEM), and an overall pressure drop. This limits the availability of the reactant from the bulk-phase to the catalyst layer, thus impacting the mass transport resistance.

Due to the presence of gradients in electrolyte content, reactant partial pressure, and temperature, nonuniform local operating conditions develop across the electrolyzer. As a result, local variations arise in mass transport and apparent activation resistances, as well as in membrane resistance, which depends on the dominant charge carrier (CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻, or OH⁻).^{21–23} These variations can be phenomenologically represented through an equivalent electrical circuit in which each local region contributes a distinct resistance corresponding to the local electrochemical and transport phenomena (Figure 1C). From a physical perspective, the electrolyzer operates under a globally applied potential; that is, all points in the cell share the same voltage between equipotential current collectors. The nonuniformity of local conditions therefore results in spatial variations in current density rather than in potential. In a steady-state operation, these variations in current density reflect the gradual change in local resistances along the cell.^{24,25}

The custom-designed cell is a 50 cm² zero-gap CO₂ electrolyzer equipped with a cathode current collector fabricated as a printed circuit board. This collector contains 32 segments, each measuring the local current density independently at a given cell voltage that is applied to the whole cell equally. From an electrical point of view, cathode and anode are connected to the power source, just as in any other conventional electrolyzer cell. The voltage is applied to the cell, and current density is measured individually using a shunt resistor for each segment (calibration of the shunts is included as Figure S1, with a brief explanation of the working principle). The linear arrangement of these segments, positioned sequentially from the inlet to the outlet, enables operando, in-line mapping of the current density distribution across the cell. The effective active area of each of these segments is 1.56 cm² each, and their reading velocity is below 0.5 s for all 32 pads, allowing one to track very fast changes in the current density profile, very quickly, and in a very tight

Figure 2. Effect of current density on the (A) cell voltage, (B) current density intervals, and (C) product selectivity. Panels (D), (E), and (F) show the corresponding current density profiles at 200, 300, and 400 mA cm⁻², respectively, taken 15 min after each current interval start. The CO₂ inlet is located at pad number 1, and the outlet is located at pad number 32.

space. A view of the custom-designed current collector, including the associated circuitry, is included in Figure S2.

The cathode current collector includes seven intermediate sampling points, evenly spaced, and located in the middle of the electrolyzer, connected to a mass spectrometer for online measurement of the local cathode gas composition. The instrument withdraws a negligible gas volume from the electrolyzer (approximately 5 mL min⁻¹), representing less than 1% of the CO₂ feed rate. Gas sampling is managed through a 3D-printed component integrated into the cell equipped with printed capillary conduits. This printed part also accommodates the cathode inlet and outlet connections and functions as an electrical insulator for the cell. Figure 1A shows the cell assembly and its assembly principle, while Figure S3 provides a complete view of the assembled cell.

The cell was tested for CO₂ electrolysis, specifically for the conversion of CO₂ to CO. In all experiments, the cathode consisted of silver nanoparticles spray-coated onto a Sigracet 39BB gas diffusion layer (GDL) and operated in a zero-gap configuration (Figure 1B). A PiperION (40 μm) membrane was used as the separator. The anode catalyst, Ir-black, was spray-coated onto a porous titanium layer (titanium frit). During the operation, CO₂ was supplied from a heated source maintained at 60 °C. The anolyte, a 0.05 M CsHCO₃ solution, was continuously recirculated through the anode compartment

at a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹ cm⁻² and 60 °C. The cell was operated galvanostatically at various current densities (200, 300, 400 mA cm⁻²). The cathode gas outlet was analyzed continuously using an online process gas analyzer, periodically calibrated with predefined CO₂, CO, and H₂ gas mixtures (Figure S4). All further experimental details are provided in the Supporting Information.

First, the effect of the employed current density on the cell performance was investigated. The applied current density was increased sequentially from 200 mA cm⁻² to 300 mA cm⁻² and then to 400 mA cm⁻² (Figure 2B). The inlet CO₂ flow rate was maintained at 12 mL min⁻¹ cm⁻² throughout these experiments. Cell voltage and selectivity results are shown in Figure 2A and C, respectively. The cell voltage values are within the range typically observed for such zero-gap electrolyzers at these current densities,^{26–28} while the CO-selectivity is exceptionally high (note that only trace amounts of H₂ were detected), which results in CO/H₂ ratio of over 200! Figure 2D, E, and F present the current density distribution profiles at each operating condition; this is 200, 300, and 400 mA cm⁻², respectively. In all cases, CO₂ entered the cell from the left and passed through the active area—perpendicular to the pads—exiting at Pad 32. Figure 2D indicates that even at relatively low current density, significant inhomogeneities in the current distribution are present. The standard deviation from the

Figure 3. Concentration profile at (A) 200 mA cm⁻², (B) 300 mA cm⁻², and (C) 400 mA cm⁻², together with the averaged outlet. These were taken 15 min after each step, in the span of ~30 min, once steady-state was reached at 2.75, 2.87, and 3.00 V.

Figure 4. Effect of CO₂ feed flow rate (B) on (A) cell voltage and (C) selectivity. Panels D–G show the corresponding current density profiles at normal 10, 8, 6, and 4 cm³ min⁻¹ cm⁻², respectively, taken 15 min after each flow rate interval start. The electrolyzer current density during the entire period was 400 mA cm⁻². The vertical dashed lines represent the change in flow rate.

intended set current density (200 mA cm⁻²) is 29 mA cm⁻². The absolute value of this deviation increases with higher current densities, reaching 47 mA cm⁻² at 300 mA cm⁻² (Figure 2E) and 55 mA cm⁻² at 400 mA cm⁻² (Figure 2F). This deviation becomes more pronounced toward the outlet region (Pad 22 onward), resulting in a marked decrease in local current density. Interestingly, despite these variations in the current distribution, the average selectivity toward CO remained high, as mentioned before.

Areas of higher current density in the electrolyzer indicate a consistent variation in the cell's overpotential resistances. Factors such as mass transport limitations, activation overpotentials, membrane resistance, geometric deviations, or a combination of these contribute to an increased resistance to current flow in the latter part of the cell, resulting in a lower local current density. In addition, we examined the influence of anolyte flow direction by reversing it after 1 h of operation

(400 mA cm⁻²) and analyzing the resulting current density profiles. A consistent downward trend from the cathode gas inlet to the outlet was observed under both operating modes. The corresponding profiles (Figure S5), followed by a more detailed description of the methodology, are provided in the Supporting Information.

In-situ experimental measurement of current density decrease along the channel has not been reported previously in the literature, but its occurrence has been analyzed through Multiphysics models. Several authors have modeled the changes in local current density along the channel of electrolyzers in gas diffusion electrodes, for CO₂ to CO conversion, showing similar downward curves to those presented in this work.^{29,30} These works suggest a sharp decline in local current density in the initial length of the electrolyzer, although the specific profile decrease varies greatly with different potentials and catalyst layer characteristics.

Figure 5. Concentration profile at normal (A) $8 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, (B) $6 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and (C) $4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, together with the averaged outlet. These were taken 15 min after each step in the span of ~ 30 min. Cell was operated at 400 mA cm^{-2} .

Subsequently, we performed an online, operando analysis of the concentration of products in the cathode compartment, for the same current densities. For this purpose, the sampling points, which are distributed across the length of the electrolyzer from inlet to outlet, are in the middle of the width. The extracted cathode gas amount remained always below 1% of the nominal CO_2 electrolyzer feed, to avoid disturbing the electrochemical performance. The sampled gas is passed through a condenser to remove water and then analyzed by using an online mass spectrometer. Further details on the sampling methodology are covered in the SI, together with a simplified system diagram (Figure S6).

Figure 3 illustrates the spatial evolution of product concentrations across the electrolyzer, as measured at the sampling points and at the outlet, for three different current densities once steady-state is reached. In all cases, a progressive consumption of CO_2 is observed along the reactor pathway, accompanied by the formation of CO. Naturally, this trend becomes more pronounced at higher current densities, with local CO_2 depletion taking place. Specifically, at 300 mA cm^{-2} , CO_2 is nearly exhausted by the outlet sampling points, while at 400 mA cm^{-2} , depletion occurs around sampling point 6. Note again that no flow pattern was employed in this case. As shown in Figure 3B,C, the low CO_2 concentrations in the latter stages of the reactor lead to a shift in selectivity toward the HER. Notably, there is a mismatch between the concentration of products from the sampling points (even the last one before the exit) and the averaged outlet. This mismatch, which is discussed more in depth in what follows, suggests nonuniform reactant distribution within the cathode compartment.

To further analyze the effect of CO_2 starvation on the current density profile, the CO_2 feed rate was varied. Starting from an inlet flow rate of $12 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which yielded high selectivity toward CO and a steady-state cell voltage of 2.92 V, the CO_2 feed was decreased stepwise to 10, 8, 6, and $4 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. At the lowest flow rate, achieving 100% faradaic efficiency (FE) for CO is stoichiometrically impossible; this experimental design was intended specifically to study the effects of the availability of CO_2 on hydrogen evolution. As the CO_2 flow rate decreased, selectivity toward CO dropped sharply initially and then stabilized after a few minutes, while parasitic HER became more pronounced (Figure 4C). This effect was most significant at the lowest flow rates (6 and $4 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), where the CO/ H_2 ratio fell below 3.

Corresponding trends were also observed in the spatially resolved current density profiles. Figure 4D–G shows the stabilized current density distributions, recorded 15 min after each flow rate adjustment, for 10, 8, 6, and $4 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ intervals. In Figure 4E, the last one-third of the electrolyzer, which previously exhibited sluggish activity, begins to recover as the CO selectivity decreases. In Figure 4F, a pronounced current density peak develops in the third part of the electrolyzer, the previous most inactive region, which becomes even more prominent when the CO_2 feed is further reduced to $4 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 4G). This result highlights the importance of an adequate CO_2 feed in electrolyzers, not only to maintain high selectivity, but also to ensure a uniform current distribution across the cell. It must be noted that with changing the CO_2 feed rate, the CO_2 pressure also changes within the cathode compartment.

The local current density acquisition software refreshes the complete current density profile every 0.33 s. This high resolution enables very fast observation of changes in the current distribution, allowing for the accurate tracking of dynamic trends within the electrolyzer. Throughout these experiments, the evolution of the current density profile could be monitored in real time, providing direct insight into how long the electrolyzer took to respond to variations in the CO_2 feed flow rate change. As shown in Figure 4, the system's response to feed changes is not instantaneous; rather, both the cell voltage (Figure 4A) and CO selectivity (Figure 4C) require a few minutes to reach a new steady state. Correspondingly, the local current density distribution undergoes a similar transition before stabilizing into a new steady-state profile, over several minutes, when changing the CO_2 flow rate from 8 to 6 normal $\text{cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In Figures S7–S9, we recorded the transition phase of the current density profile for 10 to 8, 8 to 6 and 6 to 4 normal $\text{cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. These transitions to changes in operational parameters are also included in the Supporting Information, as a short video covering the changes throughout the measurement in Figure 4.

The underlying cause of this delayed stabilization is complex and convoluted. We hypothesize that a variation in the local current density implies a change in the summed local resistance, which is determined by the cathodic and anodic mass transport resistances, activation overpotentials, and membrane resistance. Given that the change in CO_2 feed flow rate is confined to the cathode, changes in anodic resistance could arguably be neglected. Therefore, the

Figure 6. Cathode gas online analysis. (A) Flat cathode current collector; gas is forced through the GDE. (B) Modified collector with serpentine flow field, design drawing in Figure S11. All online measurements were taken at 400 mA cm^{-2} , $12 \text{ normal cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Error bars represent the standard deviation from at least three independent measurements.

observed evolution in the current density profile likely arises from a combination of variations in the cathodic mass transport resistance, local activation energy barriers, and membrane resistance.

Figure 5 presents the concentration profiles of products under the conditions of CO₂ starvation, evaluated at a nominal current density of 400 mA cm^{-2} . Three CO₂ feed scenarios were investigated, corresponding to CO₂ flow rates of 8, 6, and 4 normal $\text{cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The associated current density distributions, which exhibit trends consistent with those shown in Figure 4E–G, are provided in Figure S9. These results are consistent with the behavior previously observed in Figure 3: as local CO₂ availability decreases, the system increasingly favors hydrogen evolution, resulting in H₂ becoming the predominant product. In addition, as the CO₂ feed rate is reduced, the onset of hydrogen is displaced to earlier sampling points. This shift is more pronounced at lower CO₂ feed rates and appears to influence the current density profile, including the emergence of localized peaks (see Figure S10). These findings are in accordance with previous reports of CO₂ electrolysis mapping,³¹ but the emergence of current density spikes due to the lower thermodynamic potential of hydrogen is a new observation here.

The concentration profile corresponding to a CO₂ feed rate of $4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is particularly noteworthy. From approximately sampling point 4 (located in the center of the active area) onward, H₂ becomes the dominant gas species, accounting for over 90% of the detected products. This observation suggests local CO₂ depletion in the latter stages of the reactor under these operating conditions. Of particular interest is the potential relationship between this phenomenon and the local distribution of the electrolyte within the gas diffusion layer, which may play a critical role in modulating product selectivity and current density locally. An interesting approach in this sense would be to analyze the product distribution with the local relative humidity.³²

As shown in Figure 3, there was a mismatch between the concentrations measured at the interim sampling locations and

the outlet of the electrolyzer. Although the trends—CO formation, CO₂ consumption, and H₂ production—were consistent, the concentrations at the sampling points were significantly higher. This suggested that CO₂ was not evenly distributed across the cell's transversal axis, likely due to poor flow distribution. To address this, we tested a modified cathode current collector featuring a serpentine flow field to improve the reactant distribution. Figure 6 compares results obtained by using two different cathode flow field configurations. Both analyses were carried out under identical conditions, namely, a nominal current density of 400 mA cm^{-2} , an operation temperature of $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and a dry CO₂ feed of $12 \text{ normal cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In Figure 6A, the flat cathode current collector is used (Figure 1A, component 9), as in all measurements presented so far, as a benchmark. In Figure 6B, this component is modified with a serpentine flow field (technical drawing in Figure S11), which is generally employed in different gas-fed electrolyzers.

For both configurations, we observe a clear concentration gradient along the sampling channel, consistent with plug-flow reactor behavior, in which CO₂ is progressively consumed and converted to CO and a small amount of H₂ as the gas moves downstream, which is consistent with the concentration profiles shown before. The H₂ fraction remains low across all sampling points but increases slightly toward the outlet. When no flow field is employed, product concentrations measured at individual sampling points inside the cell are substantially higher than those found at the outlet (right part of Figure 6A). This indicates a nonuniform gas distribution within the cell, having regions where CO₂ can pass without reaction. Such heterogeneity suggests uneven reactant access and limited mixing, leading to spatial variations in the conversion and selectivity. More specifically, we hypothesize that there is a substantial amount of the CO₂ that bypasses the active area, through the areas of least resistance in the gas diffusion electrode. The reasons for these areas of less gas-flow resistance in the electrode are not clear, but they can range from defects on the homogeneity of the electrode void

channels, wide tolerances in the current collectors and/or uneven compression pressure being applied on the electrode or, more interestingly, the disruption brought by a saturation of electrolyte content in the cathode compartment (or “flooding”).^{33,34}

In order to rule out the influence of the cell architecture on the cathode gas (possible) improper distribution, we simulated the CO₂ feed flow through the external cell port and GDE. This way, we demonstrated that the reported results are not a product of the cell architecture. The results of these, along with the experimental details, are collected in Figures S13 and S14, along with a technical drawing specifying the design of the cathode insulator plate (Figure S12).

We hypothesize that wetted regions in the GDE restrict CO₂ gas transport by reducing the effective gas diffusion pathways, even if they do not completely block its flow. Beyond this, persistent flooding can create isolated liquid pockets where local concentrations change (e.g., the concentration of diluted CO₂ decreases) due to limited convective exchange. Such conditions can lead to shifts in local selectivity and modifications of the gas flow pattern by water physically blocking the previously available pathways.³⁵

Consequently, measurements taken within the channel provide a more accurate picture of local reaction efficiency and concentration, while outlet sampling captures a mixed, averaged composition. These findings emphasize the importance of reactor design and the need of applying a flow field to achieve uniform gas distribution all over the cell.

Introducing a serpentine flow field (Figure 6B)—a configuration widely used in fuel cells,^{36,37} water electrolyzers,^{38,39} and increasingly in CO₂ electrolysis⁴⁰—substantially improves gas distribution.

Variations in current density and selectivity across the X–Y plane can lead to transversal gradients in species concentration. We hypothesize that the serpentine channels primarily serve to collect electrolyte⁴¹ and remix species concentrations during electrochemical operation, promoting a more uniform gas distribution, consistent with the results shown in Figure 6.

The serpentine channel then promotes uniform CO₂ transport and minimizes spatial concentration gradients, particularly in the transversal axis, resulting in product compositions at internal sampling points that closely match the outlet. It is also clear that the flow-field is suboptimal since locally much higher conversion rates can be achieved without this flow field (Figure 6A).

CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE STEPS

We demonstrated the inhomogeneity of current density distribution in a custom designed CO₂ electrolyzer cell and its variations with respect to nominally applied current density and reactant starvation. We observed a consistent trend in product formation along the length of the electrolyzer, and the tendency is toward CO₂ starvation and product accumulation. We have shown that upon CO₂ starvation, there is a rapid growth in the hydrogen concentration in subsequent sampling locations. Interestingly, this is coupled with a spike in the current density signals in the area, suggesting a link between CO₂ depletion, selectivity decrease, and current density changes, all within a local area of a larger electrolyzer cell. We have also explored that the system is highly dynamic, continuously changing local current densities. In addition, several minutes are necessary to achieve stable current density

profiles when there is a change in operational parameters such as the CO₂ feed flow rate.

When comparing the interim values with the outlet, averaged concentration, it becomes evident that the flow distribution of the cathode gas is not homogeneous, leading to dead volumes or bypasses, which in turn reduce the overall yield of the electrolyzer cell. We hypothesize that the inhomogeneities observed in the concentration profile are not due to pure flow limitations but are electrochemical in nature. This is discussed below.

Water accumulation in the GDE limits the transport of CO₂ by forcing access primarily through diffusion. Reduced CO₂ availability can shift the selectivity toward hydrogen, consistent with the trends shown in Figure 5. Additionally, blocked diffusion pathways alter the cathode gas flow, generating additional inhomogeneities in concentration.

Several authors have demonstrated water accumulation and salt deposition for zero-gap CO₂ electrolyzers.^{42,43} But their dynamic occurrence within the whole GDE area has been scarcely reported. In this direction, operando synchrotron radiation imaging of the electrolyte and gas distribution demonstrated the heterogeneous accumulation of crystals, electrolyte, and bubbles through the entire GDE.⁴⁴

Looking ahead, critical questions still need to be addressed. Variations in local resistances and water accumulation across the entire active area should be systematically investigated to better understand concentration and current density gradients, ultimately enabling the more efficient operation of CO₂ electrolyzers. Further research should focus on elucidating the mechanisms of cathode gas transport, examining how these pathways are influenced by electrochemical factors, and determining their impact on local current density and product selectivity. Integrating advanced diagnostic tools like the one presented here, and modeling approaches could provide deeper insights into these phenomena, paving the way for improved cell designs and operational strategies.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acseenergylett.5c03770>.

Supporting video (MP4)

Additional information on the electrolyzer cell and additional electrochemical data (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Csaba Janáky – Department of Physical Chemistry and Materials Science, University of Szeged, Szeged 6720, Hungary; eChemicles Zrt, Szeged 6726, Hungary; Email: janaky@chem.u-szeged.hu

Authors

Pedro Arias Villaroel – Department of Physical Chemistry and Materials Science, University of Szeged, Szeged 6720, Hungary; eChemicles Zrt, Szeged 6726, Hungary

Egon Kecsenvity – eChemicles Zrt, Szeged 6726, Hungary

Complete contact information is available at:

<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.5c03770>

Notes

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): C.J. is a co-founder of eChemicles, while E.K. and P.A.-V. are employees. eChemicles is scaling up its patented CO₂ electrolyzer technology to provide an environmentally and economically sustainable alternative to fossil fuel-based chemicals.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is part of the European Marie Skłodowska-Curie network MiEl. The MiEl project received funding by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101073003. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Project no. RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00009, titled National Laboratory for Renewable Energy has been implemented with the support provided by the Recovery and Resilience Facility of the European Union within the framework of Programme Széchenyi Plan Plus.

REFERENCES

- (1) Raya-Imbernón, A.; Samu, A. A.; Barwe, S.; Cusati, G.; Fódi, T.; Hepp, B. M.; Janáky, C. Renewable Syngas Generation via Low-Temperature Electrolysis: Opportunities and Challenges. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2024**, *9* (1), 288–297.
- (2) Samu, A. A.; Kormányos, A.; Kecsenovity, E.; Szilágyi, N.; Endrődi, B.; Janáky, C. Intermittent Operation of CO₂ Electrolyzers at Industrially Relevant Current Densities. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2022**, *7* (5), 1859–1861.
- (3) Belsa, B.; Xia, L.; García de Arquer, F. P. CO₂ Electrolysis Technologies: Bridging the Gap toward Scale-up and Commercialization. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2024**, *9* (9), 4293–4305.
- (4) Jouny, M.; Luc, W.; Jiao, F. General Techno-Economic Analysis of CO₂ Electrolysis Systems. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2018**, *57* (6), 2165–2177.
- (5) Pachamuthu, S.; Gao, J.; Ozden, A.; Legrand, U.; Favaro, M.; Isaacs, M.; García de Arquer, F. P.; Azenha, C.; Mendes, A.; Sargent, E. H.; Janáky, C.; Grätzel, M.; Jiménez Calvo, P. Scaling Low-Temperature CO₂-to-Syngas Electroreduction: Insights into Engineering Bottlenecks and Mitigation Strategies. *ChemRxiv* **2025**, na.
- (6) Ayyub, M. M.; Hursán, D.; Saccoccio, M.; Mezzavilla, S.; Janáky, C.; Seger, B. Unlocking the Future: A Commercial Take on R&D for Emerging Electrochemical Technologies. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2025**, *10* (8), 3670–3680.
- (7) Kas, R.; Star, A. G.; Yang, K.; Van Cleve, T.; Neyerlin, K. C.; Smith, W. A. Along the Channel Gradients Impact on the Spatioactivity of Gas Diffusion Electrodes at High Conversions during CO₂ Electroreduction. *ACS Sustain Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *9* (3), 1286–1296.
- (8) Simonson, H.; Klein, W. E.; Henckel, D.; Verma, S.; Neyerlin, K. C.; Smith, W. A. Direct Measurement of Electrochemical Selectivity Gradients over a 25 cm² Copper Gas Diffusion Electrode. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2023**, *8* (9), 3811–3819.
- (9) Kimmel, B.; Garcia-Sanchez, D.; Morawietz, T.; Schulze, M.; Biswas, I.; Gago, A. S.; Friedrich, K. A. Opportunities of in Situ Diagnostics and Current Distribution in Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers with Segmented Bipolar Plates. *Appl. Energy* **2025**, *380*, 125106.
- (10) Karimi, V.; Qvistgaard, C. H.; Schmidt, S.; Wolfertz, A.; Parker, J. D.; Tetsuya, K.; Hayashida, H.; Shinohara, T.; De Angelis, S.; Tengattini, A.; Sharma, R.; Fedrigo, A.; Helfen, L.; Morgen, P.; Andersen, S. M.; Theil Kuhn, L. Unveiling the Local Effects of PTL Passivation in PEM Electrolyzers through Gas and Current Mapping

Using Operando Neutron Radiography and Polarized Neutron Imaging. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2025**, *17* (36), 50742–50752.

- (11) Minnaar, C.; De Beer, F.; Bessarabov, D. Current Density Distribution of Electrolyzer Flow Fields: In Situ Current Mapping and Neutron Radiography. *Energy Fuels* **2020**, *34* (1), 1014–1023.

- (12) Wang, Y. Da; Meyer, Q.; Tang, K.; McClure, J. E.; White, R. T.; Kelly, S. T.; Crawford, M. M.; Iacoviello, F.; Brett, D. J. L.; Shearing, P. R.; Mostaghimi, P.; Zhao, C.; Armstrong, R. T. Large-Scale Physically Accurate Modelling of Real Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell with Deep Learning. *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14* (1), na DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-35973-8.

- (13) Khetabi, E. M.; Bouziane, K.; François, X.; Lachat, R.; Meyer, Y.; Candusso, D. Analysis of Local Current Density, Temperature, and Mechanical Pressure Distributions in an Operating PEMFC under Variable Compression. *Appl. Energy* **2025**, *394*, 126187.

- (14) Kiani, M.; Zhao, Y.; Zhang, R. Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells: Recent Developments and Future Perspectives. *Chem. Commun.* **2025**, *61* (52), 9392–9411.

- (15) Chatenet, M.; Pollet, B. G.; Dekel, D. R.; Dionigi, F.; Deseure, J.; Millet, P.; Braatz, R. D.; Bazant, M. Z.; Eikerling, M.; Staffell, I.; Balcombe, P.; Shao-Horn, Y.; Schäfer, H. Water Electrolysis: From Textbook Knowledge to the Latest Scientific Strategies and Industrial Developments. *Chemical Society Reviews* **2022**, *51*, 4583–4762.

- (16) Endrődi, B.; Kecsenovity, E.; Samu, A.; Halmágyi, T.; Rojas-Carbonell, S.; Wang, L.; Yan, Y.; Janáky, C. High Carbonate Ion Conductance of a Robust PiperION Membrane Allows Industrial Current Density and Conversion in a Zero-Gap Carbon Dioxide Electrolyzer Cell. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *13* (11), 4098–4105.

- (17) Subramanian, S.; Middelkoop, J.; Burdyny, T. Spatial Reactant Distribution in CO₂ electrolysis: Balancing CO₂ utilization and Faradaic Efficiency. *Sustain Energy Fuels* **2021**, *5* (23), 6040–6048.

- (18) Ehlinger, V. M.; Lee, D. U.; Lin, T. Y.; Duoss, E. B.; Baker, S. E.; Jaramillo, T. F.; Hahn, C. Modeling Planar Electrodes and Zero-Gap Membrane Electrode Assemblies for CO₂ Electrolysis. *ChemElectroChem* **2024**, *11* (7), na DOI: 10.1002/celec.202300566.

- (19) Heßelmann, M.; Bräsel, B. C.; Keller, R. G.; Wessling, M. Simulation-Based Guidance for Improving CO₂ Reduction on Silver Gas Diffusion Electrodes. *Electrochemical Science Advances* **2023**, *3* (1), na DOI: 10.1002/elsa.202100160.

- (20) Gyenes, P.; Samu, A. A.; Hursán, D.; Józó, V.; Serfőző, A.; Endrődi, B.; Janáky, C. Flooding Revisited: Electrolyte Management Ensures Robust Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2025**, *18* (14), 7124–7135.

- (21) Garg, S.; Giron Rodriguez, C. A.; Rufford, T. E.; Varcoe, J. R.; Seger, B. How Membrane Characteristics Influence the Performance of CO₂ and CO Electrolysis. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2022**, *15*, 4440–4469.

- (22) Hansen, K. U.; Cherniack, L. H.; Jiao, F. Voltage Loss Diagnosis in CO₂ Electrolyzers Using Five-Electrode Technique. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2022**, *7* (12), 4504–4511.

- (23) Larrazábal, G. O.; Strøm-Hansen, P.; Heli, J. P.; Zeiter, K.; Therkildsen, K. T.; Chorkendorff, I.; Seger, B. Analysis of Mass Flows and Membrane Cross-over in CO₂ Reduction at High Current Densities in an MEA-Type Electrolyzer. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11* (44), 41281–41288.

- (24) Heßelmann, M.; Bräsel, B. C.; Keller, R. G.; Wessling, M. Simulation-Based Guidance for Improving CO₂ Reduction on Silver Gas Diffusion Electrodes. *Electrochemical Science Advances* **2023**, *3* (1), na DOI: 10.1002/elsa.202100160.

- (25) Freunberger, S. A.; Santis, M.; Schneider, I. A.; Wokaun, A.; Büchi, F. N. In-Plane Effects in Large-Scale PEMFCs. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2006**, *153* (2), A396.

- (26) Giron Rodriguez, C. A.; Kani, N. C.; Moss, A. B.; Joensen, B. O.; Garg, S.; Deng, W.; Wilson, T.; Varcoe, J. R.; Chorkendorff, I.; Seger, B. Insights into Zero-Gap CO₂ Electrolysis at Elevated Temperatures. *EES Catalysis* **2024**, *2* (3), 850–861.

- (27) Endrődi, B.; Kecsenovity, E.; Samu, A.; Darvas, F.; Jones, R. V.; Török, V.; Danyi, A.; Janáky, C. Multilayer Electrolyzer Stack

Converts Carbon Dioxide to Gas Products at High Pressure with High Efficiency. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, *4* (7), 1770–1777.

(28) Fernández-Caso, K.; Díaz-Sainz, G.; Alvarez-Guerra, M.; Irabien, A. Electroreduction of CO₂: Advances in the Continuous Production of Formic Acid and Formate. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2023**, *8*, 1992–2024.

(29) Hurkmans, J. W.; Pelzer, H. M.; Burdyny, T.; Peeters, J.; Vermaas, D. A. Heating Dictates the Scalability of CO₂ Electrolyzer Types. *EES Catalysis* **2025**, *3* (2), 305–317.

(30) Agarwal, V. G.; Haussener, S. Quantifying Mass Transport Limitations in a Microfluidic CO₂ Electrolyzer with a Gas Diffusion Cathode. *Commun. Chem.* **2024**, *7* (1), na DOI: [10.1038/s42004-024-01122-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s42004-024-01122-5).

(31) Subramanian, S.; Middelkoop, J.; Burdyny, T. Spatial Reactant Distribution in CO₂ electrolysis: Balancing CO₂ utilization and Faradaic Efficiency. *Sustain Energy Fuels* **2021**, *5* (23), 6040–6048.

(32) Wheeler, D. G.; Mowbray, B. A. W.; Reyes, A.; Habibzadeh, F.; He, J.; Berlinguette, C. P. Quantification of Water Transport in a CO₂ electrolyzer. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *13* (12), 5126–5134.

(33) Hao, S.; Elgazzar, A.; Ravi, N.; Wi, T. U.; Zhu, P.; Feng, Y.; Xia, Y.; Chen, F. Y.; Shan, X.; Wang, H. Improving the Operational Stability of Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction Reaction via Salt Precipitation Understanding and Management. *Nat. Energy* **2025**, *10* (2), 266–277.

(34) Disch, J.; Bohn, L.; Koch, S.; Schulz, M.; Han, Y.; Tengattini, A.; Helfen, L.; Breitwieser, M.; Vierrath, S. High-Resolution Neutron Imaging of Salt Precipitation and Water Transport in Zero-Gap CO₂ Electrolysis. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13* (1), 6099.

(35) Weber, A. Z. Improved Modeling and Understanding of Diffusion-Media Wettability on Polymer-Electrolyte-Fuel-Cell Performance. *J. Power Sources* **2010**, *195* (16), 5292–5304.

(36) Wang, C.; Zhang, Q.; Shen, S.; Yan, X.; Zhu, F.; Cheng, X.; Zhang, J. The Respective Effect of Under-Rib Convection and Pressure Drop of Flow Fields on the Performance of PEM Fuel Cells. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, na DOI: [10.1038/srep43447](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep43447).

(37) Rocha, C.; Knöri, T.; Ribeirinha, P.; Gazdzicki, P. A Review on Flow Field Design for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells: Challenges to Increase the Active Area for MW Applications. *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2024**, *192*, 114198.

(38) Hu, R.; Wen, C.; Ye, Z.; Qi, Y.; Zhang, B.; Kang, K.; Gao, Y.; Wang, D.; Tu, Z. A Comprehensive Review of Flow Channel Designs and Optimizations for Water Electrolysis Technology. *Appl. Energy* **2025**, *400*, 126643.

(39) Wang, Y.; Wang, Z.; Qiao, J.; Li, H.; Wang, X.; Cao, B.; Zhu, T.; Zhang, B.; Wang, M. Materials and Flow Fields of Bipolar Plates in Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Water Electrolysis: A Review. *Energy Reviews* **2025**, *4* (2), 100132.

(40) Wang, R.; Yuan, S.; Xue, R.; Cheng, M.; Yan, X.; Shen, S.; Guo, Y.; Zhang, J. A 3D Numerical Study on Flow Field Designs in Zero-Gap CO₂ Electrolyzers. *Energy Fuels* **2025**, *39* (8), 3942–3953.

(41) Yuan, S.; Wang, R.; Xue, R.; Wu, L.; Zhang, G.; Li, H.; Wang, Q.; Yin, J.; Luo, L.; Shen, S.; An, L.; Yan, X.; Zhang, J. Flow Field Design Matters for High Current Density Zero-Gap CO₂ Electrolyzers. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2024**, *9* (12), 5945–5954.

(42) Joensen, B. Ó.; Zamora Zeledón, J. A.; Trotochaud, L.; Sartori, A.; Mirolo, M.; Moss, A. B.; Garg, S.; Chorkendorff, I.; Drnec, J.; Seger, B.; Xu, Q. Unveiling Transport Mechanisms of Cesium and Water in Operando Zero-Gap CO₂ Electrolyzers. *Joule* **2024**, *8* (6), 1754–1771.

(43) Hao, S.; Elgazzar, A.; Ravi, N.; Wi, T. U.; Zhu, P.; Feng, Y.; Xia, Y.; Chen, F. Y.; Shan, X.; Wang, H. Improving the Operational Stability of Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction Reaction via Salt Precipitation Understanding and Management. *Nat. Energy* **2025**, *10* (2), 266–277.

(44) Hoffmann, H.; Paulisch, M. C.; Gebhard, M.; Osiewacz, J.; Kutter, M.; Hilger, A.; Arlt, T.; Kardjilov, N.; Ellendorff, B.; Beckmann, F.; Markötter, H.; Luik, M.; Turek, T.; Manke, I.; Roth, C. Development of a Modular Operando Cell for X-Ray Imaging of

Strongly Absorbing Silver-Based Gas Diffusion Electrodes. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2022**, *169* (4), 044508.